

9 September 2008

**Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)
Providing Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program**

Revised Program Plan for Year 1 of Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885

1 April–31 December 2008 (*nine-month year*)

Final Draft

This program plan describes tasks projected for the first year (1 April–31 December 2008) of ARCUS' five-year Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885 to provide organizational support to the NSF OPP Division of Arctic Sciences to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education activities. The narrative organizes projected activities into four main task categories:

1. **Arctic Community Science Planning** – coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries; includes SEARCH Coordination and Arctic Data Coordination activities.
2. **NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination** – specific coordination and support for the OPP Division of Arctic Sciences programs; includes ARCSS Program Coordination, Arctic Natural Science Program Coordination, Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination, and Arctic Section Science Materials.
3. **Arctic Science Education** – development and coordination of arctic-focused educational activities; includes broad Arctic Science Education Activities and the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series.
4. **Information and Outreach** – information and outreach activities; includes *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo listserve, Directory of Arctic Researchers, Internet Media Archive, and Arctic Community Outreach.

An additional fifth category is the provision of core support for ARCUS' NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the costs incurred by program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 **SEARCH Coordination**

The Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) is an interagency effort to understand the nature, extent, and future development of the system-scale change presently seen in the Arctic. As the SEARCH Project Office, ARCUS works closely with the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC); the Observing Change, Understanding Change, and Responding to Change Panels; various *ad hoc* working groups; and Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC) members to coordinate SEARCH science planning, implementation, and outreach activities.

Activities in the first program year of this CA focus on follow-up to discussions at the “Arctic Observation Integration Workshops” held in March 2008, including implementation of the SEARCH Sea Ice Outlook, SEARCH SSC activities, coordination with relevant national and international efforts, SEARCH representation at relevant meetings, and ongoing planning discussions and website updates:

- a. **Arctic Observation Integration Workshops (Task completed)** –
 - i. Provide travel support for invited workshop participants attending “Arctic Observation Integration Workshops” held 17–20 March 2008 in Palisades, NY (<http://www.arcus.org/search/Meetings/2008/aow/index.php>) whose travel costs were not funded through their NSF award. Over 70 participants attended the workshop series, which included three interrelated meetings: (1) a 1.5–day NSF AON investigator meeting; (2) a 1/2-day internationally-focused workshop, jointly sponsored by the AON and SEARCH for DAMOCLES (S4D) programs, on optimizing deployment of Lagrangian platforms; and (3) a 1.5–day workshop, jointly sponsored by the NSF AON program, the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program, and S4D, to improve understanding of recent arctic sea ice change.
 - ii. Worked with the workshop co-chairs to draft, edit, incorporate participant input, and finalize the final workshop report, which is available online as a PDF at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2008/aow/report.php>. Hardcopy versions of the PDF were distributed to workshop participants and by request.
- b. **2008 Sea Ice Outlook Effort** – In response to a key recommendation of the Arctic Observation Integration Workshops, provide “Central Outlet” functions for the 2008 Sea Ice Outlook. Led by Jim Overland, NOAA, the Sea Ice Outlook is an international effort to provide an integrated, community-wide summary of the state of arctic sea ice over the 2008 summer season. Central Outlook functions include development and maintenance of the Outlook website, editing and formatting of monthly Outlook content for publication online, and creation of short monthly summary statements. The Sea Ice Outlook website is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/index.php>. A small working group (15–20 people) meeting will be convened this fall or winter to undertake a retrospective analysis of the effort; this activity will be discussed further with the IPMC Chair and SEARCH SSC Chair prior to implementation.
- c. **SEARCH SSC Meeting** – Organize and implement the fall face-to-face SEARCH SSC meeting, tentatively planned for the late October timeframe in the Washington, D.C. area, including creation of a short post-meeting online report. This SSC Meeting will focus on

advancing full SEARCH implementation—assessing current activities that meet SEARCH science priorities, identifying gaps that remain, prioritizing science needs, and identifying mechanisms for further implementation, including ways to address “Understanding Change” and “Responding to Change” implementation. Specific agenda items and goals for the SSC meeting will be determined in collaboration with the SEARCH SSC Chair, SSC Members, Panel Chairs, and IPMC Chair.

d. ***Coordination with Relevant National and International Efforts***

i. ***SEARCH for DAMOCLES (S4D)*** – Continue S4D coordination activities, as outlined in the S4D scope of work. Specific activities in this program year will include:

- Provide travel support for Matt Berman, SEARCH Understanding Change Panel co-chair, to attend a “Human Impacts S4D Workshop”, to be held 15–16 September in Oslo, Norway.
- Assist in planning and preparations of a short S4D Steering Committee meeting in conjunction with the DAMOCLES General Assembly, to be held late November 2008 in Poland. Support and coordinate travel for the SEARCH SSC Chair and 3–4 additional SEARCH representatives.
- Work with DAMOCLES leadership to link SEARCH and DAMOCLES project databases, as requested by Jean-Claude Gascard, DAMOCLES lead PI.
- Invite relevant participation of DAMOCLES representative(s) to the fall 2008 SEARCH SSC Meeting (DAMOCLES representatives will pay for their own travel expenses).

ii. ***Assist with Gathering U.S. SEARCH Comments to ISAC Science Plan*** – Assist in gathering U.S. SEARCH input (i.e., comments from SSC, Panel, IPMC members) to the draft International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) Science and Implementation Plan, which is currently being drafted by Maribeth Murray, ISAC Executive Director, and the ISAC Science Steering Group; the first draft of the ISAC plan, for which SEARCH input will be requested, is expected in summer 2008.

e. ***SEARCH Participation in Relevant Conferences***

- i. ***AAAS*** – As follow-up to discussions at the Arctic Observation Integration Workshops, provide travel support for Peter Schlosser, SEARCH SSC Chair, at a session on “Terrestrial Response to Rapid Climate Change in the Arctic,” to be held during the AAAS 2008 Arctic Science Conference, 15–17 September in Fairbanks, AK. See Appendix A for the AAAS session description.
- ii. ***SAON*** – Provide travel support for Peter Schlosser, SEARCH SSC Chair, to represent SEARCH at the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) 3rd Workshop, to be held 15–17 October 2008 in Helsinki, Finland (<http://www.arcticobserving.org/>).
- iii. ***AGU*** – Provide coordination support for SEARCH activities at the 2008 Fall AGU Meeting, 15–19 December in San Francisco, CA, including a SEARCH poster session, a meeting of the SEARCH Observing Change Panel, and other meetings of opportunity, as needed by the SEARCH SSC and Panel members (PIs would support their own travel).

f. ***Initial Planning for Possible Fall 2009 State of the Arctic Conference*** – Continue discussions with SSC Chair and NSF on possible fall 2009 State of the Arctic Conference, with initial planning activities as appropriate.

- g. **Planning Teleconferences** – Convene monthly teleconferences with SSC Chair, and quarterly teleconferences with SSC Chair and NSF Program Manager. Assist in coordination and preparation of Panel teleconferences, as needed.
- h. **SEARCH Website** – Ongoing website updates, maintenance, and development, including monthly Sea Ice Outlook reports, information on meetings and workshops, and science news.

1.2 Arctic Data Coordination

A clear need has emerged through a number of arctic planning activities, conferences, and meetings for improved arctic data coordination and management across disciplines, research programs, and agencies, with activities that capitalize on developments in cyberinfrastructure concepts and tools. Year 1 of the Cooperative Agreement will focus on facilitating coordination among ongoing arctic data management efforts to reduce redundancy, and providing a coherent framework for future developments; activities include planning for an Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory Workshop, convening a small *ad hoc* working group to discuss coordination of community efforts, and documentation of the IARPC GIS database of U.S. arctic observing activities.

- a. **Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory Implementation Workshop** – Community planning discussions regarding data management and coordination have increasingly focused on a conceptual framework that would advance the integration of knowledge to answer questions about how the Arctic functions as an integrated system. These community discussions, including a major planning workshop in April 2007, have culminated in recommendations for the development of an *Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory*. The *Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory* is envisioned an “umbrella” structure that fosters interactions among arctic scientists and other stakeholders; integrates data analysis and modeling activities; provides outreach, education, and policy-relevant resources; and offers training and professional development for the arctic science community. See Appendix B for more information on the Collaboratory concept, including a letter from the ARCSS Committee to Simon Stephenson and a short summary of the April 2007 workshop.

Activities in this Cooperative Agreement year focus on lead-up activities for a second Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory Workshop planned for early winter 2009 (Jan/Feb timeframe); the overall goal of this workshop is to develop an implementation plan and recommendations for the Collaboratory, including a conceptual and procedural framework and specifications, design of the individual Collaboratory components and their interactions, and prioritization of activities for use in a broad set of research, policy, and education applications. Specific tasks in this program year will include:

- i. Convene 2–3 Organizing Committee teleconferences to refine the workshop prospectus, which will include detailed information on the workshop scope, objectives, expected participants, and products.
 - ii. Convene an open community eTown Meeting and/or AGU Town Hall to solicit input on workshop planning and Collaboratory development, as appropriate.
- b. **Arctic Data Working Group** – Convene a small, temporary *ad hoc* working group, composed of representatives of major efforts related to arctic data management (e.g., from the Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory planning group, ARMAP, CADIS, etc.) to discuss improved coordination of overlapping arctic data and information activities. One

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major topic of discussion will be sharing and linking of current databases and products in order to avoid duplication of effort. Specific activities in this program year will include 1-2 teleconferences to determine short-term steps for improving coordination between ongoing efforts, and a possible meeting of opportunity for those members already traveling to the fall 2008 AGU meeting.

- c. ***GIS of Arctic Observation Activities*** – Follow-up on initial development of the Geographic Information System (GIS) of U.S. observing activities that was created for the U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report “Arctic Observing Network (AON): Toward a US Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing”:
 - i. Begin development of Federal Geographic Data Committee (FGDC)–compliant metadata documentation of GIS layers.
 - ii. Initiate discussion with IARPC, NSF, and relevant groups (SEARCH SSC, etc.), on if and how the GIS may be developed as an effective community science planning tool for SEARCH and other relevant efforts.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination

The Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program addresses the physical, chemical, biological, and social processes of the Arctic and how these arctic systems interact with the Earth as a whole, including changes in the arctic system and their global ramifications. ARCUS provides community science management and coordination of activities for the NSF Arctic System Science Program and serves as the ARCSS Science Management Office (SMO). Program coordination activities are designed to sustain an effective system-science effort and foster high levels of community input and strong interdisciplinary collaboration

2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination

- a. **ARCSS Committee Coordination:**
 - i. Convene approximately monthly ARCSS Committee teleconferences, or as needed, to discuss ARCSS planning and move forward Committee activities. Specific agenda topics and teleconference goals will be determined in consultation with the ARCSS Committee Chair and NSF Program Director.
 - ii. Organize and convene an online ARCSS Committee Meeting in fall/winter 2008 to discuss ARCSS Program science activities, priorities, and future directions, including discussion on future synthesis activities or “capstone” product(s).
 - iii. Work with ARCSS Committee to draft and distribute, via the ARCSS email Listserve, a “Message from the ARCSS Committee” (<http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/message.html>) to update the broad ARCSS community on ARCSS activities, as appropriate.
- b. **Community Development of “Seasonality” Effort** – Through focused community discussions over the past few years, the role of seasonality in the changing arctic system has emerged as a key unknown and a science priority in the ARCSS community. In early June, NSF announced a solicitation for research on Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System (CSAS): http://www.nsf.gov/funding/pgm_summ.jsp?pims_id=503195). To help ensure this new research effort is successful and conceptually well-integrated into the larger ARCSS Program, community development activities will be planned for this summer and fall:
 - i. eTown Meeting(s) – Plan and implement an open community eTown Meeting to provide a forum for the community to discuss seasonality science and connections to the arctic system; scheduled for 19 August 2008 (http://www.arcus.org/arcss/etm/august_08/index.html).
- c. **Ongoing Website Maintenance and Development** – Continue update, maintenance, and development of the ARCSS website.
- d. **Subawards** – Subawards to support activities of the HARC Core Office at the University of Alaska Fairbanks and ARCSS Committee chair at University California Santa Barbara (UCSB) through 31 December 2008.

The subaward to the University California Santa Barbara (UCSB) supports the activities and contributions of Dr. Joshua Schimel of UCSB. Dr. Schimel chairs the ARCSS Committee (AC) and, with ARCUS, is responsible for convening and leading two or

more AC meetings per year. Dr. Schimel works with ARCUS to plan and carry out a range of other activities related to ARCSS Program planning and community leadership, including smaller working group meetings, community eTown Meetings on specific topics, and other community science management or science planning activities as needed. The AC and ARCUS will continue to work jointly in the dissemination of relevant information to the research community. In addition, Dr. Schimel and ARCUS will work with the AC and NSF to assist in the assessment, development, and integration of new ARCSS community initiatives. Special attention will be paid to developing modeling and data coordination efforts, to articulating and coordinating overall ARCSS synthesis activities, and to the assessment and articulation of arctic system research priorities and the development of recommendations for field programs.

Specific activities of the subaward to the University of Alaska Fairbanks to support the HARC Core Office is included in Appendix C.

2.2 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination

The Arctic Natural Sciences (ANS) Program is a multidisciplinary program within the NSF Division of Arctic Sciences that supports research in the atmospheric sciences, biological sciences, earth sciences, glaciology, and oceanography. ARCUS will continue to coordinate ANS science planning activities related to the Bering Sea, a region that is ecologically diverse and economically and culturally important.

2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination

- a. ***HBEST Science Plan*** – Final editing, publication, and distribution of the HBEST (Humans-BEST) Science Plan, “*Sustaining the Bering Sea Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan*,” as a parallel plan to the BEST Science Plan. The HBEST Science Plan seeks to initiate research to elucidate the dynamic relationship between humans and the Bering Sea ecosystem. The plan outlines a research program focused on three broad themes:
 - i. Impacts on humans: How past, current, and possible future changes in the Bering Sea ecosystem affect the health and wellbeing of human communities living and depending on this region for subsistence, employment, and cultural survival.
 - ii. Human impacts: How changing human uses of the Bering Sea region affect the natural cycles of this ecosystem by moderating and/or accelerating systemic changes.
 - iii. Dynamics of human and non-human natural systems: How the human-environmental dynamic has changed through time and may change in the future due to internal and external opportunities and pressures.
- b. ***BEST-BSIERP Science Advisory Board*** – Travel for three (3) Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) PIs to Washington, D.C. for a June 2008 BEST-Bering Sea Integrated Ecosystem Research Program (BSIERP) Science Advisory Board meeting.
- c. ***BEST PI Meeting*** – Support travel for five (5) participants to the fall 2008 PI meeting to be held in Girdwood, AK. Participation for one (1) ARCUS staff for meeting support.
- d. ***eMeetings*** – Support three (3) online eMeetings for research coordination and planning.
- e. ***Miscellaneous travel support*** to address program goals, if needed.

2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination – No activities in this year.

2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

Update the Arctic Discoveries Poster – Work with NSF to update the *Arctic Discoveries* poster for use as an NSF outreach tool.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

ARCUS will continue to provide an educational leadership role within the arctic community through activities designed to bridge arctic research and education.

- a. *SACNAS Researcher Travel Scholarship* – Provide limited travel funds for up to five (5) interested arctic researchers or graduate students to participate in networking and mentoring opportunities at the Society for Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS) Annual National Conference, to be held 9-12 October 2008 in Salt Lake City, Utah (<http://www.arcus.org/education/sacnas/index.html>).
- b. *Other arctic science education and outreach activities, as needed.*

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

AVS Tours – Continuation of current program, with support for four (4) AVS tours.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS serves as a communication channel providing information about current research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community, agencies, and the public.

4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter

Publish and distribute the 2008 annual issue of *Witness the Arctic* newsletter to the 13,700 subscribers; the 2008 issue feature article is “Arctic Climate Change: Where Reality Exceeds Expectations” by Mark Serreze.

4.2 Website and Internet Resources

Continue to update website and develop new content as needed.

4.3 ArcticInfo Listserve

Continue to develop and maintain the listserv, including receiving, editing, and posting announcements to the list, which is “broadcast” only; AI has 6224 current email subscribers.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

Continue to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers, which currently contains 4,120 individual entries.

4.5 Internet Media Archive (IMA)

Continue to develop and maintain the IMA. The IMA currently contains 6,500 public photos (4,000 from TREC and PolarTREC), 450 videos, 270 audio files, 100 graphics and logos, and 28 PowerPoint presentations. There are 12,000 additional resources that are currently being processed for publication in the IMA (i.e., adding keywords, attribution, permission levels, etc.).

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

- a. ***Arctic Forum 2008*** – Support for *Arctic Forum 2008* on “Tipping Points—The Arctic and Global Change,” including publication of abstract volume. The 2008 *Arctic Forum* was attended by 171 in-person participants from seven countries and over 65 online participants, representing an extensive array of organizations and agencies, including local, state, federal and international governments, private entities, universities, research institutions, press, and non-profit native organizations.
- b. ***Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall Meeting*** – Provide and organize a “Community Meeting Space” for the fall 2008 AGU Meeting to encourage scientific collaboration and to make face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community. During the week of AGU, a small conference room (accommodating 20–30 people) will be reserved, tentatively at the San Francisco Marriott, a location central to AGU sessions. This room will be available by appointment for groups working on arctic research or science education planning activities, with scheduling priority to groups directly related to NSF-funded programs.

ARCUS hosted an AGU Community Meeting Space in 2005, 2006, and 2007. Over 50 groups have utilized the space, ranging from project meetings to large planning endeavors and thematically-focused meetings. A few examples of past meeting topics and groups include: ARCSS Communities of Practice, FWI Working Groups, U.S. Permafrost Association, IPY Data Policy and Management Subcommittee, IPY Education Coordination, North Pole Environmental Observatory, CliC, Unmanned Aircraft, and many others.

Feedback from users of the Community Meeting Space has been overwhelmingly positive, with many comments each year on the utility of the service to advance collaboration, networking, and enhance project outcomes.

Past meetings schedules can be found online at:

2005 - <http://www.arcus.org/arcss/AGU2005/> (room was available for ARCSS groups)

2006 - <http://www.arcus.org/communitymeetings/AGU2006/index.html>

2007 - <http://www.arcus.org/communitymeetings/AGU2007/index.html>

- c. ***Community Outreach*** at AGU and other prominent arctic or related meetings and conferences.

5. CORE SUPPORT

5.1 Core Support

Direct project-related activities that support all of the projects included under the NSF CA rather than specific projects. Core Support includes portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.

ARCUS Year 1 CA Timeline (1 April–31 December 2008)

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 SEARCH Coordination

ARCUS Year 1 CA Timeline (1 April–31 December 2008)

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING *(Continued)*

1.2 Arctic Data Coordination

ARCUS Year 1 CA Timeline (1 April–31 December 2008)

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination

ARCUS Year 1 CA Timeline (1 April–31 December 2008)

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION *(Continued)*

2.2.1 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination: Bering Sea Research Coordination

2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

Update the *Arctic Science Discoveries* Poster

ARCUS Year 1 CA Timeline (1 April–31 December 2008)

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS Year 1 CA Timeline (1 April–31 December 2008)

Appendix A. AAAS Terrestrial Session Description

"TERRESTRIAL RESPONSE TO RAPID CLIMATE AND LAND-COVER CHANGE IN THE ARCTIC" ARCTIC AAAS MEETING, 15-17 SEPTEMBER, FAIRBANKS, ALASKA.

Convenors: Skip Walker, University of Alaska Fairbanks, and Maribeth Murray, HARC Core Office, University of Alaska Fairbanks.

Session Background

Three major forces of change are affecting terrestrial and marine ecosystems in the Arctic: rapid climate change, rapid industrialization, particularly in relation to oil and gas development, and rapid growth of people using the Arctic landscapes, both indigenous people and people from outside the Arctic. New methods are needed to address the combined effects of these influences. This session aims to bring together investigators who are doing this in different parts of the Arctic to share their experiences and point the way forward to new approaches.

This session will include speakers from three different areas of Arctic oil and gas development to represent the Yamal Peninsula, Russia, Mackenzie River area, Canada, and the US Arctic North Slope. We hope to also have a panel discussion after the talks that would help point the way forward for understanding rapid change in the Arctic.

Appropriate topics address Arctic land-cover or studies linking the onshore and offshore environments, including modeling approaches to predict infrastructure footprints, cumulative effects of climate, sea-ice, and land-cover changes, analyses of long-term vegetation change, long-term studies of recovery following disturbance, circumpolar and regional remote-sensing approaches to vegetation change, modeling approaches to vegetation change, seasonality changes in the Arctic, human and wildlife response to changing climate and land-cover changes, industry approaches to examining cumulative effects onshore and offshore.

Call for Papers

SESSION TITLE: TERRESTRIAL RESPONSE TO RAPID CLIMATE AND LAND USE CHANGE IN THE ARCTIC.

ORGANIZERS: SKIP WALKER, UNIVERSITY OF ALASKA FAIRBANKS, MARIBETH MURRAY, INTERNATIONAL STUDY OF ARCTIC CHANGE

SESSION TIME: DAY 3, RESPONDING TO CHANGE; FULL DAY SESSION

This session invites papers dealing with the linked terrestrial and human response to rapid change and the cumulative effects of rapid change in the arctic. Papers that discuss synergistic interactions, drivers of change, feedbacks and interactions and linkages to changing seasonality and development are particularly encouraged.

The session is divided into four sections:

I. The NRC North Slope Cumulative Effects report and progress since the report.

Potential topics include:

- i. Review of the NRC process and report
- ii. The North Slope Science Initiative and progress to date
- iii. Social changes resulting from changes in sea ice and development
- iv. Infrastructure and infrastructure modeling
- v. Caribou cumulative effects modeling
- vi. Cumulative effects resulting from changes in the sea-ice and on the North Slope
- vii. Effects of changes in the marine system to shipping and off-shore

II. Cumulative effects of resource development, climate change, and reindeer herding on the Yamal Peninsula Russia and the circumpolar region.

Potential topics include:

- i. The ENSINOR project and overview of Yamal development and the issues
- ii. Considerations for cumulative effects of oil and gas development
- iii. Circumpolar vegetation patterns, NDVI, and LST
- iv. Landscape and permafrost
- v. Effects on people and reindeer
- vi. Cumulative effects of infrastructure expansion on the Yamal Peninsula
- vii. Modeling vegetation change

III. Canadian perspectives on cumulative effects.

Potential topics include:

- i. Oil and gas cumulative effects in Canada

- ii. Cumulative effects of other industrial and development activities (mining etc.)
- iii. Cumulative impacts on caribou and other terrestrial species

IV. Changing Seasonality in the Arctic

Potential topics include:

- i. Retrospective Studies of Seasonal Changes in the Arctic
- ii. Seasonal Changes in Terrestrial Systems
- iii. Sea Ice, Land Surface Temperatures and Greening along the North American Arctic Transect

Persons interested in contributing a paper to the session should contact either

Skip Walker (ffdaw@uaf.edu) or Maribeth Murray (ffmsm@uaf.edu)

Appendix B. Background Information on the Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory

**Arctic
Research
Consortium
of the
United States**

Member Institutions:

University of Alaska Anchorage
University of Alaska Fairbanks
University of Alaska Statewide
Alaska North Slope Borough
Dept. of Wildlife Management
Arctic Centre
University of Lapland
Arizona State University
Bates College
Center for Northern Studies
University of Colorado
Cold Regions Research and
Engineering Laboratory
University of Delaware
Dartmouth College
Desert Research Institute
Embry-Riddle
Aeronautical University
Foundation for Glacier
and Environmental Research
Idaho State University
Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory
of Columbia University
Louisiana State University
University of Manitoba
Marine Biological Laboratory
University of Massachusetts Amherst
University of Miami
University of New Hampshire
Northern Illinois University
Ohio State University
Oregon State University
San Diego State University
Sandia National Laboratories
Scandinavian Seminar
Smithsonian Institution
SRI International
Texas A&M University
University of Washington
Woods Hole
Oceanographic Institution
Woods Hole Research Center
**3535 College Road
Suite 101
Fairbanks, Alaska 99709
USA
907.474.1600
Fax: 907.474.1604
E-mail: info@arcus.org
<http://www.arcus.org>**

15 May 2007

Simon Stephenson
Arctic Sciences Division
Office of Polar Programs
National Science Foundation
4201 Wilson Boulevard, 755 S
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Mr. Stephenson,

I am writing on behalf of the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Committee and the organizing committee for the recent Arctic System Synthesis Workshop on New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling (sponsored by NSF and held in Seattle in early April) to summarize the key issues and consensus recommendations that emerged, and to outline some thoughts on their implementation. More details can be found in the attached summary distributed to the arctic research community shortly after the workshop and will be included in the community-reviewed report planned for publication this fall. We look forward to discussing these topics with you in greater depth when we meet on Friday, 25 May, at 2:00 p.m.

The main motivation for this workshop was the increasing focus on synthesis in the ARCSS Program, particularly with respect to the challenges of integrating large, complex, and disparate data sets to answer questions about how the Arctic functions as a system. The arctic research community has recognized the need to better support synthetic modes of inquiry, which we define to include approaches such as intercomparison studies, data integration and assimilation, arctic and Earth system modeling, and cross-disciplinary data merging that will improve arctic system understanding, predictions, and provide policy-relevant information.

The specific goal of this workshop was to bring together data provider and user communities to identify innovative approaches on data management, and address recent developments in technology and modeling that will advance arctic system synthesis and understanding. More than 50 invited and self-nominated community participants attended, representing a variety of expertise and disciplines, including perspectives on natural, social, and physical sciences; field-based, remote sensing, and modeling approaches; data management; science-policy linkages; and education and outreach. In addition, nearly 35 community members participated online through a webcast and online bulletin board.

A central recommendation that arose from the workshop was the creation of a new framework to foster data and model integration. This framework - The Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory - is envisioned as an "umbrella" concept that fosters interactions among arctic scientists and other stakeholders.

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Simon Stephenson
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The Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory would encompass many different activities, which can be categorized into four integrated functions:

1. Community Network and Synthesis "Meeting Grounds,"
2. Data and Modeling Support,
3. Education, Outreach, and Policy, and
4. Scientist Professional Development.

Each of the four Collaboratory functions could be established virtually as a distributed set of activities and build upon existing resources available through relevant organizations or agencies. Fundamentally, the Collaboratory serves as a partnership-building mechanism across the many communities served, supporting collaboration and teamwork in the arctic system sciences community. Information about each of the integrated elements can be found at <http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/message.html> as well as in the attached workshop summary.

We believe that the Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory will provide a cohesive, engaging, and inclusive framework to advance arctic system science. While the April workshop outlined a vision for the framework and supporting functions, further discussion amongst the arctic community and relevant agencies is needed on how to translate this vision into action through a clear implementation and coordination plan, including linkages with cyberinfrastructure experts and industry to outline the supporting structure, tools, phasing, and management of the Collaboratory.

The workshop participants were unanimous in their appreciation of the Arctic Division, and the ARCSS Program specifically, for supporting this planning activity, which they also recognize has implications for a broad research community, even beyond NSF.

Thanks again for your encouragement and support in this process. We look forward to meeting with you on Friday, 25 May, to discuss these recommendations and strategies for their implementation.

Sincerely,

Wendy K. Warnick
Executive Director

CC: Neil Swanberg, ARCSS Program Director

Enclosure: Preliminary workshop summary: Arctic System Synthesis workshop

7 May 2007

**Arctic System Synthesis Workshop:
New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling**

2–4 April 2007

Bell Harbor International Conference Center
Seattle, Washington

Dear Colleague:

We are pleased to announce the completion of a 2.5–day workshop supported by the National Science Foundation's Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program entitled *New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling*. This letter briefly summarizes and integrates the general recommendations emerging from the workshop as well as previous planning activities. A detailed community-reviewed report is planned for publication this fall.

Workshop Background

The main motivation for this meeting was the increasing focus on synthesis in the ARCSS Program, particularly with respect to integrating and modeling large, complex, and disparate data sets to answer questions about how the Arctic functions as an integrated system. The arctic research community has recognized the need to better support *synthetic modes of inquiry*, which we define to include approaches such as intercomparison studies, data integration and assimilation, arctic and Earth system modeling, and cross-disciplinary data merging that will improve arctic system understanding, predictions, and provide policy-relevant information. The ARCSS Committee has taken a number of steps over the past several years to provide community leadership in this area, including organizing this community workshop.

Workshop planning began in earnest following an e-Town Meeting in March 2006, at which new ideas were solicited from the community on improving the utility of arctic system data and modeling. The workshop also built on results from an AGU town meeting in December 2006 as well as an e-Town Meeting in late March of this year. Extensive background material on this effort can be found at http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/2007_data/index.html.

Workshop Goal, Focus, and Participation

The specific goal of this workshop was to:

- *Bring together data provider and data user communities to identify innovative approaches on data management and assimilation, recent developments in technology, and modeling activities that will advance arctic system synthesis and understanding.*

Workshop discussions were organized around a set of guiding questions:

1. *What are the data and modeling needs to advance synthesis-focused arctic system science?*
2. *What's currently working and what is needed in terms of applying data and modeling for analysis to advance science? What are the keys to success?*
3. *What are the practical steps forward as far as mechanisms, approaches, tools and procedures, organization, standards, and related issues?*

More than 50 invited and self-nominated community participants attended the meeting, representing a variety of expertise and disciplines, including perspectives on: natural, social, and

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physical sciences; field-based, remote sensing, and modeling approaches; data management; science-policy linkages; and education and outreach. In addition, nearly 35 community members participated online through a webcast and online bulletin board. The workshop featured four "vision" talks on the subjects of data provision, information management, data synthesis across the natural and social sciences, and education and outreach; the remainder of the dialogue combined group plenary and breakout discussion.

Workshop Recommendations

Workshop participants discussed numerous data and modeling strategies that could be implemented to promote arctic system synthesis, improved scientific understanding and prediction, and increase the utility of scientific results to policymakers, educators, students, and the public.

A central recommendation that arose from the workshop was the creation of a new framework to foster data and model integration. This framework—*The Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory*—is envisioned as an "umbrella" concept that fosters interactions among arctic scientists and other stakeholders; integrated data analysis and modeling activities; outreach, education, and policy-relevant resources; and training and development of the arctic science community.

The *Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory* would encompass many different activities, which can be categorized into four integrated functions:

- 1) *Community Network and Synthesis "Meeting Grounds,"*
- 2) *Data and Modeling Support,*
- 3) *Education, Outreach, and Policy,* and
- 4) *Scientist Professional Development.*

Discussions at the workshop focused on this four-part vision as a broad approach to addressing community needs; it is envisioned that the next step in its development would focus on implementation, including linkages with cyberinfrastructure experts and industry to outline the supporting structure, tools, phasing, and management of the *Collaboratory*.

Each of the four *Collaboratory* functions could be established virtually as a distributed set of activities, and also could take advantage of existing facilities that might sponsor some of the identified activities. Fundamentally, the *Collaboratory* serves as a partnership-building mechanism across the many communities served, building on the spirit of collaboration and teamwork in the arctic system sciences community. The *Collaboratory* would provide substantial opportunity for individuals and groups to interact and execute synthesis studies, education, and outreach. A brief description of each integrated element follows:

1. Community Network and Synthesis "Meeting Grounds"

A network that links individuals, groups, organizations, and synthesis activities distributed across the nation would enable scientists to collaborate on synthesis (single, dual or multidisciplinary approaches), develop policy-relevant information and resources, foster new research initiatives, and build interdisciplinary skills. A distributed network would enable participation and cooperation at multiple levels—from individual scholars to institutions.

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Examples of specific activities could include: online searchable scientist directories, virtual synthesis activities, virtual and in-person synthesis workshops, visiting expert program, shared digital library, discussion forums, etc. These community activities would build upon existing resources available through relevant organizations or agencies.

2. Data and Modeling Support

The *Collaboratory* would be designed with the appropriate cyberinfrastructure, information technology, data discovery and handling, and modeling resources to enable efficient combination of data and models to promote inquiry-based synthesis science and a wide array of applications. These could be housed at either individual or multiple venues, capitalizing on particular strengths that a particular facility could bring in terms of synthesis-supporting services.

Cyberinfrastructure and related tools to support the *Collaboratory* would be adaptable to new developments and flexible for a variety of applications.

Needs identified by the community include: an efficient process for researchers to submit data and metadata to a long-term archive; minimal delay in the online availability of submitted data and metadata; standardized, open, and interoperable metadata and data formats; a coherent and comprehensive venue for data discovery, whereby data can be searched through a number of user-friendly methods; recovery of stored or historical data; links to existing data archives and centers; model synchronization; a method for authentication of data quality; identification of high-priority datasets to be integrated; and tools for integration of data and models and analysis across multiple data sources, scales, and formats.

3. Education, Outreach, and Policy

Education, outreach, and policy elements are a critical part of the *Collaboratory* to increase public understanding of arctic science and to provide decision-makers with relevant and timely information about the Arctic.

Examples of activities and needs include: easy-to-use data exploration tools geared to non-scientists; audience-appropriate downloadable maps and graphics; a virtual news-conferencing center; "late breaking environmental news" catalog; online directories to facilitate interactions between reporters, scientists, and stakeholders; information on individual arctic science projects and programs; researcher profiles; and K-12 lesson plans and educational resources. These activities could be coordinated through a portal structure such as an Arctic Virtual Outreach Center (AVOC) with a focus on outreach and communication to non-scientist communities.

4. Scientist Professional Development

As state-of-the-art data sets, models, and synthesis tools will emerge from the *Collaboratory*, it will be important that the community gain expertise in new synthesis tools and approaches. Scientists at all career levels—from undergraduates to established scientists—need to keep pace with the newest developments in synthesis data integration and modeling as well as training in system-level, interdisciplinary science.

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Professional development activities could include web-based courses, short classes, online curriculum materials, or exchange programs for both students and established researchers on issues related to novel tools or methods in arctic science, policy implications of arctic system science, or training in cross-disciplinary analysis and approaches.

Next Steps and Implementation

A draft report will be generated from the findings of this workshop and earlier planning events. The draft will be circulated to the wider community for review and revised for final publication in fall 2007.

We believe that the *Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory* outlined above will provide a cohesive, engaging, and inclusive framework to advance synthesis-focused arctic system science. While the April workshop outlined a vision for the framework and supporting functions, further discussion amongst the arctic community and relevant agencies is needed on how to translate this vision into action through a clear implementation and coordination plan.

We welcome any and all inputs to these recommendations and the strategic planning document.

Sincerely:

Workshop Organizing Committee

Dave McGuire, University of Alaska Fairbanks (Workshop Co-Chair),

Charlie Vörösmarty, University of New Hampshire (Workshop Co-Chair)

Larry Hinzman, International Arctic Research Center

Marika Holland, National Center for Atmospheric Research

Maribeth Murray, University of Alaska Fairbanks

Joshua Schimel, University of California Santa Barbara

Wendy Warnick, Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.

John Weatherly, Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory

Helen Wiggins, Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.

ARCSS Committee

Joshua Schimel, University of California Santa Barbara, Chair

Jennifer Francis, Rutgers University

Marika Holland, National Center for Atmospheric Research

Joseph McFadden, University of Minnesota

Maribeth Murray, University of Alaska Fairbanks

Craig Nicolson, University of Massachusetts

Jonathan Overpeck (Past ARCSS Committee Chair), University of Arizona

Don Perovich, Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory

Mark Serreze, Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences

Michael Steele, University of Washington

Matthew Sturm, Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory

Charlie Vörösmarty, University of New Hampshire

Appendix C. HARC Core Office Activities

HARC Core Office Activities 1 January – 31 December 2008

(As subaward in ARCUS Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885)

1. **2nd Sustaining Arctic Observation Networks Workshop** – Edmonton, Canada, 9–11 April 2008. On behalf of HARC, co-chaired the chaired the Human Dimension working group follow-up session; produced the HD report.
2. **Arctic Observation Integration Workshop** – Palisades, New York, March 2008. Presented discussion and data on “Human Response to the Sea Ice Minima 2007” and chaired the “Human Dimensions and Policy” breakout group; prepared follow-up report and material for workshop report.
3. **Communication Meetings** – Various email/teleconference meetings with the HARC SSG since January 2008 for developing the summary documents from meetings over the past three years, including follow-up from the fall synthesis meeting and for planning final activities.
4. **Arctic Forum 2008** – Participated as a panelist at the 2008 *Arctic Forum* on a panel focused on “Environmental Tipping Points” and presented a poster on HARC at the poster session.
5. **AAAS Session** - Co-organize a session at the AAAS Arctic Division Conference (15–17 September 2008) on “Terrestrial Response to Rapid Climate and Land Use Change in the Arctic.” This session includes papers dealing with the linked terrestrial and human response to rapid change and the cumulative effects of rapid change in the arctic.
 - Papers that discuss synergistic interactions, drivers of change, feedbacks and interactions, and linkages to changing seasonality and development were encouraged/invited:
 - » Cumulative effects of rapid land-cover and land-use changes on the Yamal Peninsula, Russia *Donald (Skip) Walker*
 - » Cumulative Impacts of Petroleum Development on Reindeer Herding in Northwest Russia *Bruce Forbes*
 - » Spatial patterns of NDVI distribution on the Yamal Peninsula, *Martha Raynolds*
 - » Cumulative Trends and Variability of Sea Ice, Land Surface Temperatures, and Vegetation in Northern Alaska. *Uma Bhatt*
 - » Impacts of Shifting Sea Ice Conditions on Human Settlement and Land Use in Arctic North America, *Maribeth Murray*
 - » St. Matthew Island: An Archive of Paleo- and Recent Ecological Change in Oceanic Beringia, *David Klein*
 - » Developing a Decision-support Tool for Long-term Infrastructure Planning on the North Slope of Alaska, *Larry Bright*
 - » The Scenarios Network for Alaska Planning: Landscape Management Collaboration and Planning in a Climate of Change, *Nancy Fresco*
 - Panel Discussion – Walker, Forbes, Bright and 1 other TBD

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- Travel support for one (1) human dimensions researcher (Bruce Forbes)
- HARC presentation of HD research synthesis and HARC poster
- Planning meeting and teleconference for 2009 Terrestrial/Human Response workshop

6. HARC Open Meeting and SSG Meeting at Fall 2008 AGU – Convene two HARC meetings of opportunity at the fall 2008 AGU (to be held in ARCUS AGU Community Meeting Room, if available):

- HARC Open Meeting to gather community input on directions for arctic HD research and input into draft HARC Synthesis Report
- HARC SSG Meeting to discuss and finalize capstone HARC products and outcomes

In addition, HARC activities will include:

- Presentation of a HARC poster
- Invited HARC talk at Union Session U23
- * HARC funds for some salary, travel, and teleconference support

7. HARC Synthesis Report – With the HARC SSG, produce a synthesis report summarizing ten years of HARC research, priorities for research (near, medium, and long-term), assessment of state of HD research within arctic science, and a bibliography of HARC research publications. This document also will include a long-term vision/strategic plan to ensure continued and increased proposal pressure and to facilitate community awareness of opportunities for national, international, and interdisciplinary collaborative research and scholarly development in human dimensions research in the arctic.

- Make draft available for public comment winter 2009
- Make final report available as online PDF and a print run Executive Summary
- Distribute/announce via HARC website, ArcticInfo, and other relevant listserves

8. Early Career Scientist Development Workshop – In collaboration with international partners (Canada, Finland, etc.) the HARC Core Office will sponsor an International Human Dimensions of the Arctic System Workshop for the next biennial International IHDP workshop program (2010). Potential sources of workshop funding in addition to the National Science Foundation include the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada, the European Union, and UNESCO. Every second year IHDP conducts a capacity building workshop with differing foci on human dimensions research. The objectives of the workshop are to identify young researchers through a competitive announcement to expose them to human dimensions research and try to involve them actively in IHDP-related activities. The main goals of the HARC workshop are to broaden participation of the International HD community in arctic research, to highlight the potential for collaborative research within the Arctic, and to explore opportunities for new scholarship on adaptation and response to arctic change.

* HARC money for planning purposes and some travel plus workshop report production.

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9. **HARC Website** – Continued update and development of the HARC website, including development of two major resources to post on the HARC website

(<http://www.arcus.org/harc/index.html>):

- List of IPY-relevant human dimensions projects funded by NSF and also international projects.
- Critical publications (a publications database) relevant to arctic human dimensions science, with input solicited from ARCSS PIs, IPY PIs, and other members of the HD community

Activities 1 September – 31 December 2007

(To provide background information for activities planned in 2008)

1. **2006 AAAS Meeting** - American Association for the Advancement of Science 2007 Arctic Division Annual Meeting <http://arctic.aaas.org/> 24-26 September 2007, Anchorage, Alaska “Partnering for Northern Futures: Science, Policy, Education, Legacy in the International Polar Year”

Special Session: “Human Dimensions of the Arctic System – Expanding the Framework for Research.” The Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Core Office (<http://www.arcus.org/HARC/>) invited papers and/or posters that address the following questions:

- How does human dimensions research connect with research on the other dimensions of the arctic system?
- How does arctic human dimensions research connect with and inform global human dimensions research?

Papers and posters that focus on identifying and understanding linkages and feedbacks among the different components of the arctic system and among those of the global system and that highlight interdisciplinarity across physical, biological, and social sciences were encouraged:

- The Role of the Recreation System in Building Community Resilience and Adaptive Capacity, *Bill Overbaugh, Lil Alessa, Terry Chapin, Andrew Kliskey*
- The Big Pay Out: Anticipated Community Consequences of the Exxon Valedz Litigation Settlement, *Duane Gill, Liesel A. Ritchie*
- Forgetting Change: Memory, Water and the Role of Perception in the Resilience of Arctic Communities, *Lilian Alessa, Andrew Kliskey, Paula Williams, Michael Barton*
- The Arctic Water Resources Vulnerability Index (AWRVI): A New Tool for the North, *Lilian Alessa, Andrew Kliskey, Richard Lammers, Christopher Arp*
- Vulnerability and Adaptation to Climate Related Fire Impacts in Alaska, *Sarah Trainor, Stuart F. Chapin III, Henry Huntington, Monika Calef*
- Modeling the Seasonal Distribution of Caribou in Response to Climatic Conditions, *Craig Nicolson, Mathew Berman, Colin West, Gary Kofinas*
- *The Linguistic Dimension in Research on Change*, Olga Lovick and Siri Tuttle (poster)

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2. HARC Synthesis Workshop – Arlington, Virginia, 5 October 2007

The HARC Synthesis Workshop was held to foster synthesis-focused communication and interaction among Human Dimensions researchers in ARCSS and the Arctic Observing Network (AON). The result of the HARC workshop was a report summarizing key issues, common challenges, and gaps in knowledge that emerged during the workshop including recommendations for moving towards formal synthesis or new synthesis efforts.

The one-day workshop consisted of brief (10-15 minutes) plenary talks by Human Dimensions researchers and discussion in the morning, followed by a focused roundtable discussion in the afternoon. For the morning session, invited speakers gave short presentations that specifically highlighted the aspects of their project that lended themselves to synthesis and aspects that were worth exploring in a broader context.

Approximately 25-30 participants attended, including researchers from ARCSS Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) projects, the IPY Arctic Observing Network, Bering Sea Ecosystem Study (BEST) investigators, ARCSS Communities of Practice, and members of the HARC Science Steering Committee.

3. 1st Sustaining Arctic Observation Networks Workshop – Stockholm, Sweden, 12-14 November 2007. On behalf of HARC, participated with a poster and co-chaired the Human Dimensions Working groups.

4. AGU Annual Meeting – December 2007. Presented HARC poster.

Form 1030 Summary

<u>Form 1030 Category</u>	<u>From: To:</u>	<u>5-year Budget</u>	<u>Year 1 Budget</u>	<u>Year 2 Budget</u>	<u>Year 3 Budget</u>	<u>Year 4 Budget</u>	<u>Year 5 Budget</u>
Salaries							
President	A1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Executive director	A2	569,872	55,877	119,253	125,216	131,476	138,050
Other professionals	B2	2,390,777	275,900	493,087	515,059	540,055	566,676
Student	B3	79,620	16,261	14,700	15,435	16,207	17,017
Clerical	B5	461,715	12,934	103,264	109,601	115,081	120,834
Total salaries		3,501,984	360,973	730,305	765,310	802,819	842,578
Fringe Benefits							
Total salaries and fringe benefits	C	4,832,738	498,142	1,007,820	1,056,130	1,107,889	1,162,757
Permanent Equipment							
	D	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)							
	E1	459,088	65,138	124,800	98,550	86,250	84,350
Travel (foreign)							
	E2	31,314	14,475	3,900	4,106	4,313	4,519
Total staff travel	E	490,401	79,613	128,700	102,656	90,563	88,869
Participant Support Costs							
Stipends	F1	32,800	800	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000
Travel	F2	690,650	100,650	246,000	113,750	120,900	109,350
Subsistence	F3	1,015,523	127,165	327,640	167,256	196,572	196,889
Total participant costs		1,738,973	228,615	581,640	289,006	325,472	314,239
Other Direct Costs							
Materials and supplies	G1	212,300	6,810	62,290	47,800	47,850	47,550
Publication cost/ docum/dissem	G2	252,273	52,860	54,920	40,202	40,495	63,795
Consultant services	G3	343,450	51,250	86,000	85,000	59,600	61,600
Computer services	G4	85,575	31,575	13,500	13,500	13,500	13,500
Subawards	G5	108,615	108,615	-	-	-	-
Other	G6	514,901	94,501	206,350	71,350	71,350	71,350
Total other direct costs		1,517,114	345,611	423,060	257,852	232,795	257,795
Total direct costs	H	8,579,226	1,151,982	2,141,221	1,705,644	1,756,720	1,823,660
Indirect Costs (FY06 provisional 38%)	I	3,218,832	396,480	813,664	648,144	667,554	692,990
Total direct and indirect costs	J	11,798,060	1,548,462	2,954,885	2,353,788	2,424,274	2,516,650

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	<u>Year 1</u>	<u>Year 2</u>	<u>Year 3</u>	<u>Year 4</u>	<u>Year 5</u>	<u>Total</u>
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING						
1.1 SEARCH Coordination	283465	830094	318983	339164	341246	2112951
1.2 Arctic Data Coordination	28167	0	0	0	0	28167
Subtotal Direct Costs	311632	830094	318983	339164	341246	2141118
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION						
2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination						
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination	261240	329164	321504	310791	326522	1549221
2.2 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination						
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination	48380	45927	52444	63365	60799	270915
2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination						
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination	0	5575	6838	7180	8083	27678
2.4 Arctic Section Science Materials						
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	2515	12055	12658	13290	13955	54473
Subtotal Direct Costs	312135	392721	393443	394627	409359	1902285
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION						
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	25959	39970	42147	44492	47016	199585
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	13301	46265	49935	53984	58510	221997
Subtotal Direct Costs	39261	86235	92083	98476	105526	421581
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH						
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	52869	89720	91051	93382	95777	422798
4.2 Website/ Internet Resources	101419	134887	141969	148722	155781	682777
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver	8509	34612	36341	38159	40067	157688
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	3958	33783	40158	42167	45270	165336
4.5 Internet Media Archive	5241	60504	63153	65936	68857	263691
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach	222005	214811	227521	223976	238022	1126335
Subtotal Direct Costs	394001	568315	600194	612342	643774	2818624
5. CORE SUPPORT						
5.1 Core Support	94953	263854	300944	312112	323752	1295616
Subtotal Direct Costs	94953	263854	300944	312112	323752	1295616
Total Direct Costs	1151982	2141219	1705646	1756721	1823657	8579224
Total Indirect Costs	396480	813663	648145	667555	692989	3218836
TOTAL	1548462	2954885	2353788	2424274	2516651	11798060
Estimated Indirect Cost Rate	38.00%	38.00%	38.00%	38.00%	38.00%	

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.

Budget Explanation

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	Total
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING						
1.1 <u>SEARCH Coordination</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	101,832	208,764	192,671	202,303	212,418	917,988
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	27,744	44,200	13,688	14,375	9,038	109,044
Participant Support Costs	124,489	391,754	92,639	102,410	75,615	786,908
Materials and Supplies	1,000	15,400	750	750	500	18,400
Publications/Dissemination	2,500	15,400	660	750	24,100	43,411
Consulting	5,750	1,000	-	-	1,000	7,750
Computer Services	1,000	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	14,500
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	19,150	150,200	15,200	15,200	15,200	214,950
Total direct costs	283,465	830,094	318,983	339,164	341,246	2,112,951
Total indirect costs	107,717	315,436	121,213	128,882	129,673	802,920
	391,182	1,145,529	440,195	468,047	470,918	2,915,871
1.2 <u>Arctic Data Coordination</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,277	-	-	-	-	16,277
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	2,490	-	-	-	-	2,490
Materials and Supplies	150	-	-	-	-	150
Publications/Dissemination	250	-	-	-	-	250
Consulting	8,000	-	-	-	-	8,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,000	-	-	-	-	1,000
Total direct costs	28,167	-	-	-	-	28,167
Total indirect costs	10,703	-	-	-	-	10,703
	38,870	-	-	-	-	38,870
Subtotal Direct	311,632	830,094	318,983	339,164	341,246	2,141,118
Subtotal Indirect	118,419	315,436	121,213	128,882	129,673	813,623
Total Community Science Planning	430,051	1,145,529	440,195	468,046	470,918	2,954,741
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION						
2.1 <u>ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION</u>						
2.1.1 <u>ARCSS Coordination</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	106,166	185,224	186,892	196,235	206,048	880,567
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	9,650	7,800	8,213	8,625	9,038	43,325
Participant Support Costs	14,939	60,965	51,320	56,205	61,711	245,139
Materials and Supplies	120	400	375	375	375	1,645
Publications/Dissemination	220	400	330	375	375	1,700
Consulting	11,000	63,000	63,000	37,600	37,600	212,200
Computer Services	5,500	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	19,000
Subawards	108,615	-	-	-	-	108,615
Other Direct Costs	5,030	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	37,030
Total direct costs	261,240	329,164	321,504	310,791	326,522	1,549,221
Total indirect costs	57,997	125,082	122,172	118,100	124,078	547,429
	319,237	454,246	443,676	428,891	450,600	2,096,650
2.2 <u>ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION</u>						
2.2.1 <u>Bering Sea Research Coordination</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	12,273	23,359	24,527	25,753	27,041	112,953
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	2,413	2,600	2,738	2,875	3,013	13,638
Participant Support Costs	22,408	19,588	24,704	34,137	30,246	131,082
Materials and Supplies	180	140	200	250	200	970
Publications/Dissemination	7,000	140	176	250	200	7,766
Consulting	1,000	-	-	-	-	1,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	3,107	100	100	100	100	3,507
Total direct costs	48,380	45,927	52,444	63,365	60,799	270,915
Total indirect costs	18,385	17,452	19,929	24,079	23,104	102,948
	66,765	63,379	72,373	87,444	83,903	373,863
2.3 <u>ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION</u>						
2.3.1 <u>Arctic Social Sciences Coordination</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	5,575	6,838	7,180	8,083	27,678
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	5,575	6,838	7,180	8,083	27,678
Total indirect costs	-	2,118	2,599	2,729	3,071	10,518
	-	7,692	9,438	9,909	11,155	38,196

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.

Budget Explanation

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	Total
2.4 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS						
2.4.1 <u>Arctic Section Science Materials</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,215	12,055	12,658	13,290	13,955	54,173
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	300	-	-	-	-	300
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	2,515	12,055	12,658	13,290	13,955	54,473
Total indirect costs	956	4,581	4,810	5,050	5,303	20,700
	3,470	16,636	17,466	18,341	19,258	75,172
Subtotal Direct Costs	312,135	392,721	393,443	394,627	409,359	1,902,285
Subtotal Indirect Costs	77,337	149,234	149,509	149,959	155,556	681,596
Total Arctic Sciences Section	389,471	541,955	542,952	544,587	564,915	2,583,881

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 <u>Arctic Science Education Activities</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,503	23,290	24,455	25,676	26,962	110,886
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	2,413	2,600	2,738	2,875	3,013	13,638
Participant Support Costs	11,204	8,395	9,264	10,241	11,342	50,446
Materials and Supplies	250	250	250	250	250	1,250
Publications/Dissemination	90	60	66	75	75	365
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	1,000	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	14,500
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	500	2,000	2,000	2,000	2,000	8,500
Total direct costs	25,959	39,970	42,147	44,492	47,016	199,585
Total indirect cost	9,865	15,189	16,016	16,907	17,866	75,843
	35,824	55,159	58,163	61,399	64,883	275,427
3.2 <u>Arctic Visiting Speakers</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,032	15,283	16,056	16,847	17,703	70,921
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	8,269	30,982	33,880	37,137	40,807	151,076
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	13,301	46,265	49,935	53,984	58,510	221,997
Total indirect costs	5,055	17,581	18,975	20,514	22,234	84,357
	18,356	63,847	68,910	74,498	80,744	306,354
Subtotal Direct Costs	39,261	86,235	92,083	98,476	105,526	421,582
Subtotal Indirect Costs	14,919	32,770	34,991	37,421	40,101	160,201
Total Arctic Science Education	54,180	119,004	127,073	135,897	145,627	581,783

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 <u>Witness the Arctic Newsletters</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	20,169	66,020	67,351	69,682	72,077	295,298
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	100	100	100	100	100	500
Publications/Dissemination	23,600	23,600	23,600	23,600	23,600	118,000
Consulting	9,000	-	-	-	-	9,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	52,869	89,720	91,051	93,382	95,777	422,798
Total indirect costs	20,090	34,094	34,599	35,485	36,395	160,663
	72,958	123,814	125,650	128,867	132,173	583,461
4.2 <u>ARCUS Internet Resources</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	100,419	117,487	124,019	130,222	136,731	608,877
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	10,400	10,950	11,500	12,050	44,900
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	1,000	7,000	7,000	7,000	7,000	29,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	101,419	134,887	141,969	148,722	155,781	682,777
Total indirect costs	38,539	51,257	53,948	56,514	59,197	259,456
	139,958	186,144	195,916	205,237	214,978	942,233

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.

Budget Explanation

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	Total
4.3 <u>ArcticInfo Listserver</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	8,509	34,612	36,341	38,159	40,067	157,688
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	8,509	34,612	36,341	38,159	40,067	157,688
Total indirect costs	3,233	13,153	13,810	14,501	15,225	59,922
	11,742	47,765	50,151	52,660	55,293	217,610
4.4 <u>Directory of Arctic Researchers</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	3,958	31,183	37,421	39,292	41,258	153,111
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	2,600	2,738	2,875	3,013	11,225
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	1,000	1,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	3,958	33,783	40,158	42,167	45,270	165,336
Total indirect costs	1,504	12,838	15,260	16,023	17,203	62,830
	5,463	46,620	55,418	58,190	62,474	228,166
4.5 <u>Internet Media Archive</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,241	53,004	55,653	58,436	61,357	233,691
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	10,000
Consulting	-	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	20,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	5,241	60,504	63,153	65,936	68,857	263,691
Total indirect costs	1,992	22,991	23,998	25,056	26,166	100,203
	7,232	83,495	87,152	90,992	95,023	363,894
4.6 <u>Arctic Community Outreach</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,013	78,354	82,272	86,384	90,704	397,726
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	31,363	26,000	27,375	11,500	12,050	108,288
Participant Support Costs	44,816	69,956	77,200	85,342	94,518	371,832
Materials and Supplies	500	500	625	625	625	2,875
Publications/Dissemination	18,400	8,000	8,050	8,125	8,125	50,700
Consulting	4,000	-	-	-	-	4,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	62,914	32,000	32,000	32,000	32,000	190,914
Total direct costs	222,005	214,811	227,521	223,976	238,022	1,126,335
Total indirect costs	84,362	81,628	86,458	85,111	90,448	428,007
	306,367	296,438	313,979	309,087	328,470	1,554,341
Subtotal Direct	394,001	568,315	600,194	612,342	643,774	2,818,624
Subtotal Indirect	149,720	215,959	228,073	232,690	244,633	1,071,082
Total Information and Outreach	543,721	784,275	828,266	845,033	888,408	3,889,707
5. CORE SUPPORT						
5.1 <u>Core Support</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	45,537	153,608	188,980	198,429	208,351	794,906
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	6,031	32,500	34,219	35,938	37,656	146,344
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and supplies	4,510	45,500	45,500	45,500	45,500	186,510
Publications/Dissemination	500	4,820	4,820	4,820	4,820	19,780
Consulting	11,500	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	51,500
Computer Services	24,075	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	37,575
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	2,800	14,050	14,050	14,050	14,050	59,000
Total direct costs	94,953	263,854	300,944	312,112	323,752	1,295,616
Total indirect costs	36,082	100,264	114,359	118,602	123,026	492,334
Total Core Support	131,037	364,118	415,303	430,714	446,777	1,787,948
Total Direct Costs all tasks	1,151,982	2,141,221	1,705,644	1,756,720	1,823,660	8,579,226
Total Indirect Costs all tasks	396,480	813,664	648,144	667,554	692,990	3,218,833
Total All Tasks	1,548,461	2,954,885	2,353,788	2,424,274	2,516,650	11,798,058

Unit proposal number: S5665
 PI: Maribeth Murray

						Year 1
		BANNER ECLASS	Wage/HR	Leave Rate	Hours	
A. Senior Personnel (faculty)						
number of months						
2	Maribeth Murray, Principal Investigator	F9	47.40	1.5%	399	19196
0	Co-Investigator	F9	0.00	1.4%	0	0
0	Co-Investigator	F9	0.00	1.4%	0	0
0	Co-Investigator	F9	0.00	1.4%	0	0
0	Co-Investigator	F9	0.00	1.4%	0	0
A. Total Senior Personnel						19196
B. Other Personnel						
(full time = 174 hours in a month)						
number of months						
0	Classified (NonExempt Staff - Regular)	NR	0.00	21.0%	0	0
0	Classified (NonExempt Staff - Regular)	NR	0.00	21.0%	0	0
0	Exempt Staff - Regular	XR	0.00	20.7%	0	0
0	Exempt Staff - Regular	XR	0.00	20.7%	0	0
number of students						
0	Under Grad academic yr (760 hrs)	SN	0.00	0.0%	0	0
0	Under Grad in summer (560 hrs)	ST	0.00	0.0%	0	0
0	Grad Student academic yr (760 hrs)	GN	0.00	0.0%	0	0
0	Grad Student in summer (560 hrs)	GT	0.00	0.0%	0	0
B. Total Other Personnel						0
Total Salaries and Wages (A+B)						19196
C. Fringe Benefits						
Exempt Personnel Benefits					48.7%	0
Faculty Benefits					46.3%	8888
Under Grad Benefits					8.5%	0
Grad Student Benefits					8.5%	0
Classified Personnel Benefits					60.7%	0
C. Total Fringe Benefits						8888
Total Salaries and Benefits (A+B+C)						28084
D. Equipment						
D. Total Equipment						0
E. Travel						
1.	Domestic	AGU / Arctic Forum 2008				3969
		Student Travel Award				2500
						0
2.	Foreign	Oxford, UK (Food Security and Environmental Change) Edmonton, Canada (IPY Workshop Two - SustainingArctic Observing Networks) New Delhi, India (Early Career Scientist Development Wksp)				11800
E. Total Travel						18269
F. Participant Support						
F. Total Participant Support						0
G. Other						
materials & supplies						
publications						2500
consultant						
computer						
subawards						
communications, copies, animal care, analysis						1000
tuition						
number of students		\$ per credit	# of credits	Total		
1	in-state tuition	287	18	5,166		
1	out-of-state tuition	586	18	10,548		
	total tuition					0
G. Total Other						3500
H. Total Direct Costs (A-G)						49853
base						49853
I. Total Indirect Costs (F&A) MTDC x overhead rate						23680
current rate is						47.5%
J. Total Direct & Indirect (H+I)						73533

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET

FOR NSF USE ONLY

ORGANIZATION University of California, Santa Barbara				PROPOSAL NO.		DURATION (MONTHS)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/PROJECT DIRECTOR Joshua Schimel				AWARD NO.		Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PIs, Faculty and Other Senior Associates List each separately with name and title. (A.7. Show number in brackets)				NSF-Funded Person-months			Funds Requested By Proposer	Funds Granted by NSF (If Different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR		
1. Allen Doyle – Assoc. Specialist				3.5	0.0	0.0	16193	\$
2.								
3.								
4.								
5.								
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET EXPLANATION PAGE)								
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1-6)				3.5	0.0	0.0	16193	
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)								
1. (0) POSTDOCTORAL ASSOCIATES							0	
2. (0) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)							0	
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0	
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0	
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0	
6. (0) OTHER							0	
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							16193	
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							6963	
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							23156	
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)								
0								
0								
0								
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0	
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							0	
2. FOREIGN							0	
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT								
1. STIPENDS \$ 0.0								
2. TRAVEL 0.0								
3. SUBSISTENCE 0.0								
4. OTHER 0.0								
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS			0	
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS								
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES								
2. PUBLICATION/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION								
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES								
4. COMPUTER SERVICES								
5. SUBAWARDS								
6. OTHER								
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS								
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)								
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A) (SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) MTDC (Rate: 51.5, Base: \$23156)								
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)								
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)								
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECT SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)								
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)								
M. COST SHARING: PROPOSED LEVEL \$0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT: \$0				
PI/PD TYPED NAME AND SIGNATURE*			DATE		FOR NSF USE ONLY			
Joshua Schimel					INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE		Date Checked	Date of Rate Sheet	Initials-ORG	